

A Marcus Wallenberg Symposium "Quantum Theory: Advances and Problems" – QTAP**Satellite workshop "Quantum Foundations & Quantum Information" - QF&QI**

June 10-13, 2013. Arrival June 9, departure June 14

Program of Symposium and Satellite Workshop

Arranged by ICMM - International Centre for Mathematical Modeling in Physics,
Engineering and Cognitive Sciences; Linnaeus University, Sweden

See <http://lnu.se/qtap> ; <http://lnu.se/qfqi>

Organization committee, QTAP:

- *H. Atmanspacher (IGPP, Freiburg, Germany/ ETH Zürich, Switzerland)*
- *A. Khrennikov (Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden)*
- *A. Migdall (NIST, USA)*
- *A. Plotnitsky (Purdue University, USA)*
- *S. Polyakov (NIST, USA)*
- *G. Weihs (Innsbruck University, Austria)*

Organization committee, QF&QI:

- *M. D'Ariano (University of Pavia, Italy)*
- *C. Brukner (University of Vienna, Austria)*
- *E. Haven (University of Leicester, UK)*
- *G. Jaeger (Boston University, USA)*
- *A. Khrennikov (Linnaeus University, Sweden)*

Local organizing committee:

- Ekaterina Yurova (Linnaeus University, Växjö, Sweden), E-mail: ekaterina.yurova@lnu.se

Special Sessions, QTAP:

- *General Questions of Quantum Foundations, A. Khrennikov, organizer*
- *Probing the limits of quantum mechanics, G. Weihs, organizer*
- *Complementarity in Quantum Physics and Beyond, H. Atmanspacher and A. Plotnitsky, organizers.*
- *Quantum randomness: theory and experiment, A. Migdall and S. Polyakov, organizers*
- *Quantum-classical hybrids, T. Elze, organizer*

Special Session, QF&QI:

- *Quantum-like models outside physics: from cognition and information retrieval to economics and finances, P. Bruza, J. Busemeyer, E. Dzhafarov, E. Haven and A. Khrennikov, organizers.*

8.30-9.15	Registration: outside the main conference room WEBER, building K	
Weber		
9.10-9.15	<i>Opening Ceremony:</i> A. Khrennikov	
	Chairman:	<i>M. Appleby</i>
9.15-9.45	I. Bengtsson (Stockholm University, Sweden)	Quantum states as stars
09.45-10.15	C. Fuchs (Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics, Canada)	Why QBism Does Not Fear Bell's Theorem
10.15-10.45	F. De Martini (University of Rome, Italy)	Interpretation of quantum nonlocality by Weyl's conformal geometrodynamics
10.45--11.10	Coffee break	
Weber	Chairman:	<i>G. Grössing</i>
11.10-11.40	J.-Å. Larsson (Linköping University, Sweden)	Contextuality as a quantum-mechanical dimension witness
11.40-12.10	M. Ohya (Tokyo University of Science, Japan)	A mathematical realization of von Neumann's Measurement scheme
Weber	SPECIAL SESSION:	Quantum-like models outside physics
	Chairman:	<i>E. Dzhafarov</i>
12.15-12.45	J. R. Busemeyer (Indiana University, USA)	Quantum models of cognition and decision
12.50-14.15	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Weber	SPECIAL SESSION:	Quantum randomness: theory and experiment-1
	Chairman:	<i>S. Kolthammer</i>
14.15-14.45	V. Scarani (National University of Singapore, Singapore)	Bell-based randomness generation with trusted or partially untrusted seed
14.45-15.15	J. Bienfang (NIST, USA)	Quantum randomness as a public resource
15.15 -15.45	A. Ling (National University of Singapore, Singapore)	Quantum Randomness Generation on Mobile Platforms
15.45-16.15	S. Polyakov (NIST, USA)	Mode Reconstruction: The Reverse Problem of Quantum Randomness
16.15-16.45	S. Kolthammer (Oxford University, UK)	Multiphoton Quantum Walks: Experimental Boson Sampling
16.45-17.00	Coffee Break	

PARALLELL SESSIONS of workshop QF&QI		Session 1: K1040 Session 2:K1043 Session 3: K1076 Session 4: K1082
Session 1: K1040	Chairman:	<i>L. Marchildon</i>
17.00-17.20	P. Janotta (University of Wuerzburg, Germany)	Generalized probabilistic theories without the no-restriction hypothesis
17.20-17.40	S. Al-Safi (University of Cambridge, UK)	Simulating all non-signalling correlations via classical or quantum theory with negative probabilities
17.40 -18.00	G. Oas (Stanford University, USA)	Exploring Non-Signaling Polytopes with Joint Quasi-Probability Distributions
18.00-18.10	Short break	
18.10-18.30	H. Yau (FDNL Research, USA)	Reconsidering Born's Postulate and Collapse Theory
18.30-18.50	R. Romano (Iowa State University, USA)	On the completeness of quantum mechanics and the interpretation of the state vector
Session 2: K1043	Chairman:	<i>J.-Å. Larsson</i>
17.00-17.20	O. Andersson (Stockholm University, Sweden)	Spectral weighted geometric phase for mixed quantum states
17.20-17.40	H. Heydari (Stockholm University, Sweden)	Geometrical uncertainty relations for density operators
17.40 -18.00	G. Cedersund (Linköping University, Sweden)	Different interpretations of quantum mechanics have different implications for free will
18.00-18.10	Short break	
18.10-18.30	N. Harshman (American University, USA)	Observables, Entanglement and Subsystem Clustering in Few-Body Systems
18.30-18.50	G. Ch. Krizek (University of Vienna, Austria)	Ockhams Razor and the interpretations of quantum mechanics
Session 3: K1076	Chairman:	<i>A. Ling</i>
17.00-17.20	T. Hara (Tokyo University of Science, Japan)	New pseudo random number generator by using a chaos coupling map
17.20-17.40	L. Gyongyosi (Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Hungary)	The Correlation Conversion Property of Quantum Channels
17.40 -18.00	Ph.-Th. Le (National University of Singapore, Singapore)	Properties of the random seed input to Bell tests
18.00-18.10	Short break	
18.10-18.30	J. Fors (Linköping University, Sweden)	Using classical light to bypass the security tests of Franson-based quantum key distribution
18.30-18.50	A. Andersson (Max Planck Institute for Mathematics in the Sciences, Germany)	Insights from Operator Deformations in Quantum Measurement Theory

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Poster session: June 10-June 13, hall in front the main conference auditorium, Weber

Session 4: K1082	Chairman:	<i>M. Genovese</i>
17.00-17.20	H. Geurdes (CGI)	Monte Carlo study of Bell's correlation
17.20-17.40	M. Gondran (University Paris-Dauphine, France)	The double interpretation sought by Louis de Broglie?
17.40 -18.00	I .Pikovski (University of Vienna, Austria)	Probing Planck-Scale Physics with Quantum Optics

Weber		
9.05-9.20	S. Hwang (Rector of Linnaeus University, professor in physics)	Welcome Speech
	Chairman:	<i>F. De Martini</i>
09.25-09.55	M. Genovese (INRIM, Italy)	Quid est ergo tempus? An experimental approach to the nature of time in quantum mechanics
10.00--10.30	A. L'Huillier (Lund University, Sweden)	Quantum Physics with Attosecond Pulses"
10.35-11.00	Coffee Break	
Weber	Chairman:	<i>A. Zeilinger</i>
11.00-11.30	P. Delsing (Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden)	Experiments on the dynamical Casimir effect in superconducting circuits
11.35-12.05	G. Grössing (Austrian Institute for Nonlinear Studies, Austria)	Condensation of the Smoky Dragon: Sub-Quantum Currents and Cheshire Cats
12.05-12.35	M. D'Ariano (University of Pavia, Italy)	Deriving the Dirac equation without using relativity from Quantum Cellular Automata
12.40-14.00	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Weber	SPECIAL SESSION:	Probing the limits of quantum mechanics
	Chairman:	<i>P. Delsing</i>
14.00-14.30	H. Rauch (Atom Institute Vienna, Austria)	Coherence and incoherence in neutron quantum optics
14.35-15.05	A. Zeilinger (Vienna University, Austria)	Entangled Photons in Large Real and Hilbert Spaces
15.10 -15.40	G. Weihs (University of Innsbruck, Austria)	Multipath interference tests of quantum mechanics
15.45-16.00	Coffee Break	
Weber	Chairman:	<i>H. Rauch</i>
16.00-16.30	S. Ramelow (Vienna University, Austria)	Closing Loopholes in Bell Experiments
16.35- 17.05	B. C. Hiesmayr (University of Vienna, Austria)	Complementarity Reveals Bound Entanglement of Two Twisted Photons
17.05-17.35	W. Duer (University of Innsbruck, Austria)	Macroscopicity of quantum spin systems
18.00	<i>Conference dinner</i>	<i>At Teleborg Castle</i>

09.30-12.50	Invited talks in two parallel sessions	Session1: Weber Session2:K1043
Session1: Weber	Chairman:	<i>G. Weihs</i>
09.30-10.00	C. Curceanu (LNF-INFN, Italy)	Quantum explorations: From the waltz of the Pauli Exclusion Principle to the rock of the spontaneous collapse
10.00-10.30	F. Sciarrino (University of Rome, Italy)	Fundamental test of quantum mechanics with larger dimensional quantum systems
10.30-10.50	Coffee Break	
10.50-11.20	M. Kupczynski (University of Ottawa, Canada)	On a possible violation of the optical theorem in LHC experiments
11.20-11.50	K. Michielsen (University of Aachen, Germany)	Simulation of a neutron experiment confirming Ozawa's universally valid error-disturbance relation
11.50-12.20	T. Nieuwenhuizen (University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands)	Solution to the quantum measurement problem
12.20-12.50	A. I. Vistnes (University of Oslo, Norway)	Attempts to develop a classical local realism model that describe entangled photon experiments
Session2: K1043	Chairman:	<i>M. D'Ariano</i>
09.30-10.00	B. Svensson (Lund University, Sweden)	QM Weak Values - pro and con
10.00-10.30	A. Hosoya (Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan)	Weak Values and Geometry of Quantum Space
10.30-10.50	Coffee Break	
10.50-11.20	M. Ozawa (Nagoya University, Japan)	Universally Valid Reformulation of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle
11.20-11.50	P. Lahti (University of Turku, Finland)	Heisenberg's error-disturbance relation
11.50-12.20	N. Watanabe (Tokyo University of Science Corporation, Japan)	On Entropy Type Complexity of Quantum Processes
12.20-12.50	B. Khots (Compressor Controls Corporation, USA)	Observer's Mathematics applications to the Quantum Mechanics
12.55-14.00	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
Weber	SPECIAL SESSION:	Quantum-classical hybrids
	Chairman:	<i>N. Buric</i>
14.00-14.30	T. Elze (University of Pisa, Italy)	Quantum-Classical Hybrid Dynamics
14.30-15.00	L. Diosi (Academy of Science, Hungary)	Hybrid Master Equations

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15.00-15.30	N. Buric (University of Belgrade, Serbia)	Phase space theories of hybrid systems
15.30-15.50	Coffee break	
Weber	SPECIAL SESSION:	Complementarity in Quantum Physics and Beyond
	Chairman:	<i>R. E. Kastner</i>
15.50 -16.20	H. Folse (Loyola University, USA)	The Methodological Lesson of Complementarity: Bohr's Naturalistic Epistemology
16.20-16.50	A. Plotnitsky (Purdue University, USA)	Complementarity Beyond Physics and Physics Beyond Complementarity
16.50-17.20	H. Atmanspacher (IGPP, Freiburg/ETH Zürich, Switzerland)	Complementarity in Classical Dynamical Systems

Weber	Chairman:	<i>G. Adenier</i>
09.05-09.35	R. E. Kastner (University of Maryland, USA)	The Central Interpretational Problem of Quantum Mechanics
09.40-10.10	I. Volovich (Mathematical Institute of Russian Academy of Science, Russia)	TBA
10.15-10.45	G. Jaeger (Boston University, USA)	Macroscopic Realism and Quantum Information
10.50-11.10	Coffee Break	
11.10-12.50	Invited talks in two parallel sessions	Session 1: Weber Session 2: K1043
Session1: Weber	Chairman:	<i>C. Fuchs</i>
11.10-11.40	L. Marchildon (University of Quebec, Canada)	Entanglement Swapping in the Transactional Interpretation
11.45-12.15	M. Appleby (Perimeter Institute, Canada)	Towards a New Formulation of Quantum Mechanics
12.20-12.50	G. Cassinelli (University of Genova, Italy)	A new approach to the representation theorem of a quantum logic
Session2: K1043	Chairman:	<i>P- Lahti</i>
11.10-11.40	H. De Raedt (University of Groningen, The Netherlands)	Quantum theory as the most robust description of reproducible experiments
11.45-12.15	G. Adenier (University of Oslo, Norway)	Bosonic and Fermionic States with Polarization Entangled Photons
12.20-12.50	E. Rosinger (University of Pretoria, South African Republic)	Five Departures in Logic, Mathematics, thus Physics
13.00-14.15	Lunch: at Restaurant Kristina	
14.15-17.30	Parallel presentations in special session and workshop. Special session: Weber; workshop K1043	

Weber	SPECIAL SESSION:	Quantum-like models outside physics -2
	Chairman:	<i>Ch. Gallus</i>
14.15-14.45	E. Dzhafarov (Purdue University, USA)	Contextuality Embedded in the Classical Probability Theory with Multiple Sample Spaces
14.45-15.15	J. A. de Barros (San Fransisco State University, USA)	Negative probabilities and counterfactual reasoning
15.15 -15.45	K. Sato (Tokyo University of Science, Japan)	The Code Structure of Influenza A virus
15.45-16.15	Plotnitsky (Purdue University, USA)	Are quantum-like mathematical models possible or necessary outside quantum physics?
16.15- 16.30	Coffee Break	
Weber	Chairman:	<i>A. Plotnitsky</i>
16.30-16.50	Ch. Gallus (Deutsche Bank, Germany)	Modeling the state of a financial market
16.50-17.10	P. Khrennikova (University of Leicester, UK)	Quantum framework and non-separability of voters preferences in the US elections
17.10-17.30	Y. Pelosse (University of Liverpool, UK)	Quantum Like Decision-Making as an Expression of Rationality and Free Will
Workshop: K1076	Chairman:	<i>E. Rosinger</i>
14.15-14.45	O. Smolyanov (Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia)	Hamiltonian and Feynman structures in Quantum theory
14.45-15.15	A. Khrennikov (Linnaeus University, Sweden)	Born's rule from classical signal theory
15.15 -15.35	P. Rocchi (LUISS University, Italy)	Why the Subjectivist and Frequentist Views on Probability Are not Conflicting
15.35-15.55	I. Barukcic (University Of Hamburg, Germany)	Anti Einstein - Refutation of Einstein's General Relativity Theory
15.55-16.15	A. Bolotin, (Ben-Gurion University of the Negev)	Limits of reductionism and the measurement problem
16.15- 16.30	Coffee Break	
Workshop: K1076	Chairman:	<i>B. C. Hiesmayr</i>
16.30-16.50	H. Dang (Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics, Canada)	Constructing Low Dimensional Symmetric Informationally-Complete Quantum States
16.50-17.10	A. Nikkhah Shirazi (University of Michigan, USA)	Our Current Concept of Locality May be Incomplete
17.10 -17.30	A. Nenashev (Institute of Semiconductor Physics, Russia)	Understanding envariance
Weber 17.30	<i>Conference closing ceremony at Weber</i>	

Poster Session		
	A. Andersson	Insights from Operator Deformations in Quantum Measurement Theory
	M. Gondran	An experience to test the Einstein locality principle on position and momentum
	L. Gyongyosi	The Quantum Capacity of a Partially Degradable Quantum Channel
	L. Gyongyosi	Polar Codes for Partially Degradable Quantum Channels
	H. Yau	Reconsidering Born's Postulate and Collapse Theory

Information

Location:

- The conference will take place at Linnaeus University, Växjö.
- Main conference room: Wicksell, in building K.

Transportation:

From Resacentrum (located close to the train station) to the University. To come to the first lecture of morning sessions, the bus number 7 at 8.29 from Train station seems the most convenient.

By fair weather, it is also possible to walk to the university along the lakes. It takes between 40 and 50 minutes.